

Perceived Constraints on Sport Participation among Young Koreans in Australia

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Abstract—The purpose of this study was to examine a broader range of sport constraints perceived by young Koreans in Australia who may need to adjust to changing behavioral expectations due to the socio-cultural transitions. Regardless of gender, in terms of quantitative findings, the most important participation constraints within the seven categories were resources, access, interpersonal, affective, religious, socio-cultural, and physical in that order. The most important constraining items were a lack of time, access, information, adaptive skills, and parental and family support in that order. Qualitative research found young Korean's participation constraints among three categories (time, parental control and interpersonal constraints). It is possible that different ethnic groups would be constrained by different factors; however, this is outside the scope of this study.

Keywords—Constraints, cultural adjustment, Sport, Young Koreans in Australia.

I. INTRODUCTION

CONSTRAINTS in sport participation are defined as factors which preclude or limit an individual's frequency, intensity, duration, or quality of participation in sport and recreation activities [1]. The term "constraint" is differentiated from barriers [2], which generally refers to "any factor, which intervenes between the preference for an activity and participation in it" [3].

Several researchers have identified potential factors relating to sport participation and physical activity in the general population that highlight an array of social, cultural and economic circumstances that intersect to facilitate and constrain participation [4], [5]. However, the majority of the existing research has largely focused on constraining factors in the general population without much attention to problems particular to minority ethnic immigrants [6]. Stodolska [7] was of the view that much remains to be done in terms of expanding sport constraints theory to make it better suited for studying constraints among minority ethnic groups.

While some special groups such as women have generated considerable interest among sport researchers [4], [5], [8], only a few specific studies have investigated constraints of other disadvantaged groups such as young ethnic minorities [9], [10], and even fewer efforts have been directed towards studying the constraints of Korean immigrants [2].

While some newly arrived minority ethnic youths may want to play sport there can be many factors and barriers that can stop them [11]: (a) some may have come from countries

without structured community based sport and are unfamiliar with the concept; (b) lack of familiarity with sporting clubs and environments; (c) potential threat or experiences of racism; and (d) family and cultural commitments may take priority over sport.

Tsai and Coleman [5] examined the constraining factors on first generation male and female Chinese immigrants' participation in sports and recreation in Australia. Resource constraints (time and financial) and interpersonal constraints were the most important whereas physical constraints were the least important. There was also no significant correlation in perceived constraints according to gender, length of residence in Australia, financial status or age [5].

Golembki, Holderna-Mielcarek, Niezgodna and Szmatala [12] suggested that Polish youth's lack of recreational sport and other forms of exercise was due to the pressure of improving their professional qualification, and insufficient resources and leisure infrastructure. Stodolska and Jackson [13] also reported that Polish immigrants in Canada increased recreational sport participation following their settlement, but that after this initial increase, their interest in sport usually subside. The observed post-arrival changes in sport participation were attributed to past latent demand, to the decreased role of certain interpersonal constraints, and to exposure to the new leisure and sport opportunities.

Chung [9] investigated the most important sport constraints perceived by Muslim females in Hong Kong, which were access and resources constraints. 'Being watched by a male' was a matter of constraint perceived by Muslim females (it is inappropriate for Muslim males to watch females participating in sports). Muslim females used constraint negotiation strategies to overcome the problem of a lack of companions by organizing sport competitions for mosque sisters.

Tcha and Lobo [2] examined the relationship between the socio-demographic characteristics of Korean immigrants and their leisure constraints in Western Australia. They found that both were personal constraints (a) the lack of time because of work/school commitments and (b) the lack of time because family was extremely important. Gender was also found to be critical for the importance of structural constraints (information, accessibility and provision) or environmental constraints (culture, language and race-related). Socio-demographic characteristic factors were found to be in general unimportant [2]. This is possibly due to the fact that overall participation in active leisure activities by Korean immigrants is very low and they therefore do not experience constraints due to their lack of participation.

There is strong empirical evidence that ethnic minorities

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faced with a complex mix of barriers to participate in sport and are socially excluded [14]. However, less attention has been paid to factors that constrain sport participation of young Koreans (with some exceptions, see [2]). This raises the general question of constraining factors (i.e., socio-cultural, religious, access, affective, physical, resource and interpersonal), especially in reference to limiting and withdrawing from sport participation.

II. CONSTRAINTS

Crawford and Godbey's [3] categorization of three discrete models (interpersonal, intrapersonal and structural constraints) has also been widely used. Allison and Smith [15] also extended this to include the ethnic minority elderly and asserted that three different levels of constraints should be addressed: (a) psychosocial barriers, (b) cultural/intercultural barriers, and (c) institutional barriers. They also argued that, while the first barriers have been systematically addressed, more efforts should be exerted to investigate the other two barriers. Crawford, Jackson and Godbey [16] further revised this by integrating the three barriers into a single model in which participants are viewed as having negotiated a sequential and hierarchical series of constraint levels.

Due to the complexity of constraining factors, a categorization system has been widely utilized by researchers [3], [5], [15], [16]. Jackson and Dunn's [17] categorization, one of the most common, considers two different dimensions where constraints are effective: (a) constraints that hinder people from taking up leisure activities; and (b) constraints that lead to a reduction in, or discontinuation of leisure activities. Raymore, Godbey and Crawford [18] analyzed the relationship between self-esteem, gender, socioeconomic status and perceptions of constraint on leisure among adolescents.

Tsai and Coleman [5] added one more dimension of constraint to Jackson and Dunn's categorization model, however in a different way from Crawford et al. [16]. Tsai and Coleman [5] classified the constraints that hinder people from taking up new sporting activities as (a) those that inhibit people's desire to start new sporting activities (antecedent constraints); and (b) those that hinder people from taking up sporting activities that they desire to do (intervening constraints).

Henderson, Stalnaker, and Taylor [19] first identified two types of constraints: intervening barriers and antecedent barriers, however, they did not find significant evidence for the importance of antecedent barriers. In this regard, Tsai and Coleman [5] emphasized that one's desire to take up new sporting activities, their actual participation, and their decisions to continue or discontinue their participation in sport may be subject to different influences.

Tsai and Coleman [5] and Chung [9] outlined a detailed framework dividing the range of constraining factors such as interpersonal, religious, resources, affective, access, socio-cultural and physical constraints.

A. Interpersonal Constraint

Interpersonal constraints on participation in sport such as

isolation provide a potentially dislocating experience for young ethnic minority immigrants. Social networks have been found to be important facilitators of young ethnic minorities' participation in sports, with family and friends offering supportive environments for the expression and transmission of identity, that is, the retention of certain core cultural traits [20].

B. Religious Constraint

Religious constraints may include ethnic customs and religious beliefs. It is significant that a large portion of those from ethnic minorities think that religion is very important and believe that religious categories are at least as important as ethnic categories in describing themselves [9].

C. Resource Constraint

Resource constraints relate to socio-economic status, cost, time and caring responsibilities. The interplay of time and cost may prevent young ethnic minority groups from accessing sport programs and services even when they would prefer to participate [4], [5]. Time considerations include study, work and family commitments; the opening hours of many sporting facilities; and the need for young ethnic minorities to spend time travelling. Foster and his colleagues [21] reported that the lack of time was the most common barrier in all the surveys that stops people from exercising, but there are a number of more complex barriers.

D. Affective Constraint

Affective constraints relate to how appealing and meaningful people consider certain sport activities. This is obviously a critical pre-requisite for their participation in sports. Teachers and schooling environments are recognized to play an important role in facilitating equal access without involving stereotypes [22]. Young ethnic minorities may use personalized forms of information such as word of mouth for an interest in sporting activities [4].

E. Access Constraint

Access constraints relate to the provision and availability of sport facilities, information, skills and transport. Tsai and Coleman [5] identified a lack of awareness of opportunities and levels of skill and ability to participation in sports. Some authors stress the importance of sports involvement in terms of developing new skill sets as well as personal enjoyment, social interaction and social change [10]. This kind of sport participation can be difficult to achieve by young ethnic minorities because of limited public transport availability. They tend to rely on public transport because of a lack of parental support [23]. The major disadvantage of many Australian sport providers may be a lack of information and inappropriate facilities and programs for ethnic minorities. This may limit access by young ethnic minorities, while meeting the needs of the mainstream Australian population [20], [22], [24].

F. Socio-Cultural Constraint

Socio-cultural constraints refer to racial and cultural based constraints and discomfort in certain social settings, which may come from being part of ethnic minority groups within

mainstream society. Sawrikar and Muir' study [24] divided socio-cultural constraints into three sub-factors: (a) gendered and cultural expectations, (b) acculturation, and (c) direct and indirect racism.

G. Physical Constraint

Physical constraints refer to age, injury and physical problems. These fundamental physical constraints related to the evidence about increasing rates of overweight and obese young people within ethnic minorities. This has been linked with a wide range of health and social problems including isolation and marginalization [25]. Young ethnic minorities from non-English speaking backgrounds have also poor cardiovascular health compared to general population of Australians and are more likely to be inactive [11].

The constraints on leisure and sport experienced by minority ethnic immigrants and students may differ from those of the general population and other ethnic groups both with respect to their static and dynamic characteristics.

Stodolska's [7] study of assimilation and leisure constraints has suggested that static characteristics of immigrants' constraints on sport are related to the nature of their set constraints at any given point in time. These included specific constraints such as language difficulties, being unfamiliar with ways of life in the host country, as well as experiences with discrimination – these can have a significant effect on the leisure experience of new arrivals. Post-arrival stress, depression, anxiety, alienation, and often a sense of loss are likely to modify the usual constraint patterns associated with certain age groups, occupation, gender or family status groups.

Besides the static characteristics, findings of Stodolska's [7] study suggested that as immigrants become more assimilated, constraints become dynamic. The constraints set evolves as a function of factors related to the passage of time (i.e., acculturation – that is likely to affect their leisure behavior including participation patterns, motivations, and constraints) [7]. Sawrikar and Muir [24], however, suggested that the dynamic aspects of constraints should be utilized within the existing models [16] in relation to ethnic minority groups. And therefore not only the distinct nature of young Koreans' constraints, but also their dynamic nature in relation to changing acculturation levels should be addressed.

Acculturation occurs when groups of individuals from different cultures come into continuous contact with each other, and subsequently, there are changes in the original cultural patterns of either or both group [26]. Acculturation modes are: (a) assimilation - willingness to adopt positive relationships with the culture of the host country and showing a diminishing interest in their culture of origin; (b) separation - not adapting to the host culture and maintaining the ways of their culture of origin, often against difficulties; (c) integration - retaining the culture of origin as well as maintain positive relationships with the host culture; and (d) marginalization - not adapting to the host culture but neither maintaining the behaviors and values of their culture of origin.

In Washburne's [27] marginality theory, ethnicity does not take in account the effects of resource constraints on leisure

participation patterns, with differences in leisure studies resulting from variations in norms and values in ethnic/racial groups. Prejudice, discrimination, and certain ethnic characteristics can be possible constraints. Self-esteem and acculturation levels and their relationships to constraints were examined in Yu and Berryman's [10] study.

Language problems, inability to find leisure partners, lack of money or lack of awareness of existing opportunities were negatively related to self-esteem levels during their cultural adjustment, experiencing constraints not commonly found in the general population [7].

It was expected in this study that the intensity and types of one's sport participation constraints would be different depending on both static and dynamic characteristics of young Koreans.

III. PROCEDURE

A. Participants - Questionnaire

The questionnaire was able to draw comparisons and relationships between different variables in sport experiences of young Koreans (mostly students of 9 to 25 years of age) who had been in Australia for at least 6 months. The final questionnaire contains items that were organized into (a) demographics and language proficiency and (b) sport participation and constraints.

B. Measures

Demographic characteristics section asked the respondents about their age, gender, country of birth, length of residency in Australia, family composition and residential status.

Language Skills adapted a 5-point Likert type scale ('very poor' to 'excellent') which includes three subscales (i.e., speaking, reading and writing in both English and Korean) that measures the level of English and Korean language proficiency of the respondents.

Acculturation modes adapted a 5-point Likert scale ('strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree') made up of 29 items which were grouped into four acculturation modes, including assimilation (8 items), integration (5 items), separation (7 items) and marginalization (9 items). These items were adapted from the Barry's [28] East Asian Acculturation Measure (EAAM) that allowed the researcher to assess a pattern of cultural attitudes and behaviors relevant to socialization. EAAM items were also developed with satisfactory reliability and validity for the four dimensions of acculturation attitudes outlined by Berry [29].

Participation constraints adapted a 5-point Likert type scale ('never' to 'always') made up of 17 items which were grouped into seven themes, including social-cultural, religious, access, affective, physical, resources and interpersonal. These items were developed based on the references of [4], [5], [9].

Sport participation used a 5-point Likert type scale ('never' to 'more than once a week') made up of 21 specific sport activities (i.e., martial arts, racket sports, ball sports, water sports, other, etc.) that aims to measure levels of sport participation.

C. Statistical Analysis

After the survey closed, the collected quantitative data were coded and entered into a computer using Microsoft Excel and the statistical program of SAS (Version 9). Error checking and edit procedures were programmed into the data entry instrument. All of the materials contained in the questionnaires were kept in confidence and all respondents remained anonymous.

D. Follow-up Interview

The interview participants consisted out of 20 children (3 Females and 17 males) and 18 parents (6 Fathers, 12 Mothers, and 2 Absent). Among the children (5 Australian born and 15 Korean born), the mean age was 12.9 and the mean year of stay was 6.5. There were 10 primary students, 8 secondary students and 2 tertiary students, of mixed language skills. The interviews were recorded and then transcribed in full. All participants in the interviews were identified by a code number. The text-based data were analyzed using thematic analysis by means of the computer-based qualitative analytical N-Vivo tool.

IV. RESULTS

A. Main Constraints

The results concerning main categorizations of constraining factors revealed that resource constraint had the highest mean score of young Korean respondents, followed by access constraint, interpersonal constraint, affective constraint, religious constraint, social-cultural constraint then physical constraint.

In terms of main constraining factors of individual items, insufficient time due to their study/work was commonly indicated as the main factor preventing them from participating more often in sport or non-participation. The next important preventative factor was access to appropriate facilities (e.g., segregating different areas and appropriate session time), followed by a lack of information on what/where is available, a lack of adaptive skills, not have anyone to participate with (e.g., nobody to go with), parental restriction, and a lack of encouragement from family members. However, the respondents had a relatively low mean score in gender inequality and encountered racial bias for non-participation or participation more often in the 12-months prior to survey. The primary constraint concerning sport participation among young Koreans in Australia seems to be lack of time due to study.

Males and females had a similar rate of overall sport constraints and insufficient time due to study/work was the most common reason given by both males and females. Young Korean females, however, had a relatively higher score in a lack of adaptive skills and simply being 'not interested' in sport compared to their male counterparts. When asked for the main constraints for participation more often or non-participation, most mean scores showed no statistical differences between males and females. Females cited a lack of adaptive skills as the next important constraint followed by a lack of appropriate facilities, a lack of information and lack of freedom to go out

for sport through parental restriction. Males, however, cited the main factors for not participating or participation more often as a lack of information followed by a lack of appropriate facilities and a lack of adaptive skills.

B. Dynamic Nature of Young Koreans and Constraints

The preliminary data show that perceived constraining factors were only slightly affected by gender. However, it was assumed that there would be relationships between demographic characteristics and language skills, acculturation modes and perceived constraints on levels of sport participation. Correlation analyses were performed to examine the relationships between constraint categorization factors demographic variables using Pearson correlation coefficients. The socio-cultural constraint category had a significantly positive correlation with separation and marginalization at the level of 0.05.

The religious constraint category had a significantly positive correlation with assimilation at the level of 0.001 and both integration and length of cultural contact at the level of 0.5, while religious constraint had a significantly negative correlation with Korean proficiency at the level of 0.001 and age at the level of 0.01. It seems that long-stay younger-aged young Koreans (e.g., Australian-born young Koreans) who were more assimilated or integrated with lack of Korean language skills showed relatively higher levels of religious constraint.

The access constraint category had a significantly positive correlation with age only at the level of 0.05. Access to appropriate facilities, information, and transportation support seemed to be lacking among older-aged young Koreans.

The affective constraint category had a significantly positive correlation with separation at the level of 0.05, while having a significantly negative correlation with both gender and Korean proficiency at the level of 0.05. It seems that young Korean males who were more separated with lack of Korean language skills showed relative higher levels of affective constraints.

The resource constraint category had a significantly positive correlation with age at the level of 0.001 and length of cultural contact at the level of 0.05. It seems that older-aged young Koreans who stayed in Australia for a short period showed relatively higher levels of resource constraints such as lack of time to participate in sport due to study.

The interpersonal constraint category had a significantly positive correlation with assimilation at the level of 0.001 and integration at the level of 0.01, while interpersonal constraint category had a significantly negative correlation with Korean proficiency at the level of 0.01. More assimilated or integrated young Koreans who lacked Korean language skills showed relatively higher levels of interpersonal constraints.

Overall sport participation had a significant correlation with both interpersonal and religious constraints at the level of 0.01 and socio-cultural constraints at the level of 0.05. Young Koreans who were more separated or marginalized showed relatively higher levels of socio-cultural constraints.

C. Time Constraints

The main factor limiting sport participation by young Koreans in Australia was 'time'. It became apparent that the parents' high expectations for their children's future, combined with the children's own aspirations to enhance their social status, resulted in an overloaded schedule. Parents are desperate for their children to advance their social status and outperform their neighbors and peers. However, among these parents, there appears to be a general dissatisfaction with the Australian education system. Outside school hours, therefore, time is taken up with extra-curricular tutoring and computers. After-school tutors are common place and there is little or no time for leisure and sport. A 'success ladder' begins with year 3 and the advent of opportunities for selective stream entry. This is followed by ongoing pressure to achieve entry into a selective high school, followed by a prestigious university, job and so on. Korean parents tend to be very conscious of 'keeping up with the Jones's' (competing with their neighbors), as is expressed by the following comments:

Parent 9: "I worry about my kid because all his friends study hard. He needs to study harder than they do. You know, the main reason we came here was to improve his English and get him into a good university....Sport is not at the top of our list. Australian children seem to us to be naturally active and sporty. They grow up at the beach or running in the park. To Korean parents, the first thing a child should do is study hard to get an education. Their children need to study harder than Australian children because English isn't their first language."

Child (9 years old male): "I'm year 3, I have piano on Wednesdays and I am so tired after I finished my coaching class, and also it is too late to do any sport at night time. I used to do swimming twice a week but I stopped because my parents want me to go to a selective school and I have to study."

D. Parental Control Constraints

Another important factor constraining the sport participation of young Koreans in Australia proved to be 'parental control'. A relationship exists between time management, participation in different types of sport and the influence of the parents on the young Koreans in Australia. The use of modal operators by their parents to coerce specified action is representative of their dominant influences, as is apparent in the following interview response:

Child (10 years old male): "My friend started doing taekwondo so my parents said that I had to go too."

Parent 15: "They do it because I tell them to... No argument."

Within the Korean-sub culture, cultural separation can be a result of its support networks being drawn from a limited set and peer pressure being common among the parents as a

motivating factor in the choices concerning their children's sport. This is reflected in the following comments:

Parent 2: "Because as immigrants we are an isolated group, we tend to stay together. When my child's friend started taekwondo class we just followed."

E. Interpersonal Constraints

Young Koreans also involved in mainstream sports are significantly constrained by interpersonal factors. Many young Koreans in Australia believe that they are ill-prepared to communicate in English with native speakers, although previously studying English in Korea. This, again, leads to marginalization and poor outcomes in the mainstream sporting environment. The following comment is representative of this important constraining factor.

Child (16 years old male): "If someone has poor language and communication skills, they may be socially outcast and isolated. I think I would have to learn more about the culture and language before I could comment on that. For example, At school, there's a group of people who have poor English skills because they only recently arrived in Australia and they usually just hang out by themselves and do not sport or interact much with anyone else...mostly the non-English speaking Korean people. There are some people, who have problems with understanding some sporting terms in English. When the coach tells a Korean player to do something and he doesn't understand it would cause a problem in the actual game. I also have problems with some of the other kids and I often feel alone."

V. DISCUSSION

This study supported the idea that immigrant populations are subject to certain constraints that are not found or to appear differ in the general population [7]. In general, resource, access and interpersonal constraints were given more weight than others. As with the current study, Tcha and Lobo's [2] investigation of Western Australian Korean immigrants found that lack of time because of work/school commitment and family influenced their sport and leisure participation. This study's findings are consistent with the literature, in that during adolescence, the most important constraining items were a lack of time followed by access, information, adaptive skills, and parental and family support in that order. As the group was not homogeneous, different weight was given to different constraining factors depending on levels and types of sport participation, however, time constraint proved to be a constant. This study extended Tcha and Lobo's work in that an interrelationship was found between study, parental and peer expectation, language difficulties, religious requirement, education systems, school curricula, lack of access and facilities, cultural practices, personal aspirations, fatigue and stress.

Previous studies have identified various constraining factors related to sport participation across different demographic

groups. The research findings from the participation constraints analysis indicated that young Korean females had limited sport participation opportunities due to a perceived lack of adaptive skills compared with their male counterparts. This concurs with Malina's [30] explanation of this lower involvement by females citing differences in body image, physical abilities and attitudes. The traditional role division within the migrant family sees women as homemakers, having insufficient time to develop skills necessary for successful integration into the new society [31]. In this study, a lack of appropriate sport facilities, information, and parental restriction served as constraining factors encountered by young Korean females in Australia. In addition, they may also face physical constraints including lack of childcare facilities and general safety and security issues.

The present study found a relationship between gender and sport participation, and a relationship between sport participation and parental influence. It is possible, therefore, to speculate that Korean parents exert different levels of influence concerning the types and levels of sport participation depending on the gender of their children. It is interesting to point out that similarities exist between sporting culture and Korean culture in Australia in that both are, by and large, patriarchal in nature. Young Koreans sampled in this study indicated that inequality between males and females existed. This may be linked to Confucianism as a social creed in Korea which sharply separates the domestic sphere from the public and subordinates females to male, creating and extremely masculine-dominate culture [32].

Some Korean women may still be pressed into this Confucian stereotype with their social life (sport included) organized under men's dominion. Korean culture has a long history of an ideology that has justified inequality between men and women. Sport today in Korea maintains the prejudice that males are a breed apart and also perpetuates patriarchy by reinforcing gender inequalities [32]. Walseth [33] found that the main reason for not participating in sport by females from minority groups was home and family responsibility, whereas for men it was the demands of work and study.

Apart from the general results that the perceived importance of religious and interpersonal constraints are positively associated with levels of assimilation and integration, while socio-cultural and affective constraints are positively associated with levels of separation and marginalization and that the constraints set found among young Koreans differs somewhat from that of the mainstream, several more specific observations can be derived from the results of this study.

The findings supported the notion that more assimilated or integrated young Koreans may perceive constraints (for example, in ability to find a partner or lack of time due to religious practices) limiting their active participation in sport. They may feel withdrawal or limited from new or existing sport opportunities available both inside and outside their community. On the other hand, more marginalized or separated young Koreans who may perceive constraints such as lack of desire to start participating in sport due to racial discrimination, language barriers and cultural distance with members of the mainstream, may not engage in new sport opportunities. The

findings supported the research of Horton [34] suggesting a sense of marginalization or exclusion is the likely result due to disadvantaged minority culture.

While young Koreans faced with the complex mix of constraints to participate in sport during their acculturation process, Tcha and Lobo's [2] study is one of the few investigations that explicitly includes socio-demographic characteristic factors and questions their importance. In contrast with Tcha and Lobo, the present study supported the idea that the socio-demographic variables can account for levels of constraint categorisations. Older-aged young Koreans demonstrated higher levels of resource and access constraints and they tended not to participate in sport. In addition, young Koreans with higher levels of assimilation tended to perceive interpersonal constraints to be of lesser importance than their counterparts. This finding can be potentially explained by the fact that more assimilated young Koreans who participate in sport actively would perceive better interpersonal relations with their sport partners of mainstream.

Even within a cultural group, different traditions and interpretations may produce unique sets of barriers to sport participation [23]. Among the Korean-Australian community there is a diversity of language, ethnicity, religion and cultural heritage. The Korean community, however, lacks experience and resources in assisting young Koreans. There is a tendency to formulate and implement their 1.5/second generation support projects concerning sport without properly understanding the cultural sensibilities and conformity in the host society.

Ethnic minority groups are prone to different treatment in Australian society due to social structures are not equally accessible to all. These may lead to "exclusionary behavior by the majority, separatist behavior by the minority and the formation of ghettos" [35], and may be the source for racial discrimination. In particular, the perceived importance of access constraints was found to be higher among older-aged young Koreans. Language constrains the extent to which minority ethnic youths may overcome participation barriers (e.g., lack of knowledge about sites or information about particular sporting activities) [10]. Some short stay older-aged young Korean participants who have lower levels of assimilation may feel frustrated when they face having to learn in an English-only sport environment. Brochures advertising various facilities and programs can be hard to decipher, resulting in missed opportunities, limited access and progress. Application forms may be submitted without supporting information such as term and conditions, family medical history, emergency details, exercise history, purpose, etc. Inadequate counseling due to language barriers can prevent effective problem solving and subsequent participation.

Factors that can lead to withdrawal or limited access for both active and potentially active participants were found in this study. It would therefore be useful in the future to examine modes of constraints from two perspectives: (a) those which limit those who participate in sport actively; and (b) those which limit those inactive individuals who are potentially participants.

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